

Comparative multiphase flow analysis of dry and wet marine exhaust systems based on thermal, pressure, and turbulence characteristics

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Abstract

This study employs CFD to compare dry and wet marine exhaust systems under identical conditions: a 15 m/s exhaust velocity at 470 °C and a 125 mm pipe. The dry exhaust, discharging into the air, forms a buoyant plume extending approximately five pipe diameters with temperatures exceeding 200 °C downstream. Jet velocity remains above 5 m/s at 4D, and turbulence kinetic energy decreases by ~30% over the same distance. In contrast, the wet exhaust submerged in seawater cools below 60 °C within 2D, and jet velocity drops under 2 m/s by 1.5D. A localized static pressure rise of +12 kPa at the outlet is observed, approximately 100 times greater than the <0.12 kPa disturbance in the dry case. Turbulence decays by ~80% within 2D downstream of the wet exit. Dry exhaust ensures efficient plume dispersion with minimal back-pressure but risks deck contamination, whereas wet exhaust provides thermal suppression and signature reduction at the expense of higher engine load. Future work should explore transient, three-dimensional simulations for improved design guidance.

Keywords: CFD, Marine exhaust systems, Multiphase flow, Thermal dispersion, Turbulence.

1. Introduction

Marine vessel exhaust systems play a crucial role in safely expelling engine gases and managing both environmental emissions and onboard thermal effects. In recent years, increasingly stringent regulations have targeted ship exhaust pollutants due to their harmful impact on air quality and human health (Jeong et al. 2023). Beyond atmospheric pollution, the high-temperature gases emitted can also pose hazards to the ship itself: for instance, hot exhaust plumes can contaminate the hull, damage antennas, and degrade the crew's working environment if not properly directed (Dobrucali 2021; Köse 2020). On many ships, the funnel is located above or within the superstructure. Aerodynamic interactions between the exhaust flow and the ship's structure can create low-pressure, recirculating zones that trap exhaust gases on deck (Park et al. 2011). This trapped hot gas can lead to overheating of nearby equipment and even interfere with instruments like anemometers or helicopter operations (Dobrucali 2012). Such problems have been documented on modern vessels where design constraints cause exhaust downwash and stagnation around the deck. These issues underscore the importance of exhaust system design in protecting both the environment and shipboard safety (Scott, White, and Owen 2015).

Marine exhaust configurations generally fall into two categories: dry exhaust systems, which release hot gases directly to the atmosphere, and wet exhaust systems, which use water to cool and/or route exhaust gases (Cambaz, Görgülü, and Arat 2021). Most large commercial ships employ dry, above-deck exhaust stacks. In contrast, certain high-performance or military vessels use wet exhaust designs to achieve specific benefits (Correia et al. 2021). For example, the Royal Malaysian Navy's patrol vessels, corvettes, and frigates commonly incorporate a seawater cooling system for engine exhaust (AKMI Corporation 2025). In these systems, exhaust gases are refrigerated by a water jacket or direct injection before being expelled underwater, dramatically reducing the gas temperature and volume. The volume reduction makes mixing with the surrounding water more efficient, which diminishes the visible plume and thermal signature of the exhaust. Indeed, a primary motivation for wet exhausts on military ships is to reduce infrared and smoke signatures for stealth, as well as to lower exhaust noise. The cooled, denser exhaust in a wet system tends to remain submerged and less detectable, in contrast to a hot buoyant plume from a dry stack. However, wet exhaust designs bring their own challenges: they require managing water ingress and back-pressure, and often a dual-outlet system is needed. For instance, in some naval designs, the exhaust is diverted to an above-water outlet during low-speed maneuvers or reverse motion to prevent backflow when underwater discharge is ineffective. Careful engineering is needed to balance these trade-offs so that neither crew safety nor engine performance is compromised (Ismail 2016).

Several studies in the literature have applied computational and experimental methods to understand and improve ship exhaust system performance. Bayraktar et al. analyzed the gas turbine exhaust of a warship using both analytical formulas and CFD, demonstrating that a full-scale 2D CFD model could successfully capture the exhaust flow's velocity, pressure, and temperature fields (Bayraktar et al. 2007). Their simulations, performed in FLUENT with a steady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (RANS) approach, allowed visualization of flow patterns such as velocity vectors and heat distribution, and enabled calculation of pressure losses along the exhaust path. This work showed that CFD is an effective tool for such analyses, matching analytical predictions of pressure drop within a few millibars. Park et al. carried out a parametric CFD study on an 8,000 TEU container ship to investigate exhaust gas dispersion around the vessel (Park, Yang, and Rhee 2017). They examined factors like ship loading, wind speed/direction, and funnel geometry (height and shape), and quantified how exhaust fumes could recirculate and cause deck contamination under adverse conditions. Notably, their study found that insufficient funnel height on ships with integrated deckhouse–funnel designs leads to exhaust gases being drawn down onto the

deck, posing risks to crew and equipment. As a result, Park et al. (2017) recommended a design guideline of maintaining the exhaust outlet height at least twice the height of the deckhouse to avoid significant exhaust gas contamination on the decks. Such guidance highlights how small design changes can greatly mitigate onboard pollution. Ismail (2016), on the other hand, focused on the thermal aspects of a wet exhaust system. In his study of a naval vessel's exhaust heat exchanger, a coupled CFD and structural analysis was used to evaluate how cooling the exhaust with seawater affected thermal stresses. The research showed that while water-cooling the exhaust can drastically reduce gas temperatures, it can induce high thermal gradients in the exchanger material, sometimes exceeding yield stress if not properly designed. This underscores that wet exhaust systems must be engineered to handle not only fluid flow, but also the structural stresses from rapid cooling. The literature illustrates the spectrum of considerations for exhaust systems: from flow-induced pressure losses in dry stacks, to dispersion of pollutants around the ship, to the heat transfer and structural implications of water-cooled exhausts. Building on these prior works, this study presents a direct computational comparison between a traditional dry exhaust and a water-cooled exhaust under equivalent conditions. The aim is to elucidate how the presence of water as the exhaust receiving medium alters the flow patterns, pressure distribution, and thermal dispersion of the exhaust plume, and to draw conclusions that can inform better exhaust system design for both commercial and naval applications (Bayraktar et al. 2007; Ismail 2016; Park et al. 2011).

2. Materials and Methods

The engine powering the examination was based on a Scania DI-13 marine diesel engine, commonly found in small patrol craft and harbor vessels, providing approximately 426 kW at 1,800 rpm. In the dry exhaust configuration, gas exits vertically through the exhaust stack and goes directly into ambient air. In the wet exhaust model, the exhaust is discharged underwater at a 15° downward angle, as per Scania's installation guidelines for wet systems. The entire system conforms to the two different exhaust configurations outlined in the manual: namely, the dry stack and the wet discharge system, allowing direct comparison under identical engine conditions. The 15° incline ensures gradual entry into water, minimizing abrupt pressure spikes, consistent with Scania's recommended layout (Scania CV AB 2017). The exhaust pipe used in both wet and dry scenarios has an inner diameter of 125 mm, consistent with documentation from the Scania marine installation manual. The layout includes a vertical rise to 350 mm above the centerline, followed by a 1020.6 mm slanted section, and finally a 15° downward incline where the pipe discharges either into air or water, as shown in the geometry schematic. These dimensions ensure consistency between the computational model and practical installations recommended by Scania, and they facilitate direct comparison between the two exhaust types under identical geometric constraints.

The CFD simulations in this study were performed using ANSYS Fluent 2022. A steady-state, RANS approach was employed to model the flow and heat transfer in the exhaust plumes. To capture the interface and interaction between exhaust gas and water in the wet case, the Volume of Fluid multiphase model was used. The turbulence effects were resolved with the Shear Stress Transport $k-\omega$ model, which is well-suited for flow separation and free-surface flows. Gravity was included (set as -9.81 m/s^2 in the vertical Y-direction) to account for buoyancy forces on the hot exhaust and to simulate the correct stratification of the air-water environment. The use of a full-scale two-dimensional domain allowed a high-resolution mesh to be used while keeping computational cost reasonable, consistent with previous studies that showed 2D models can adequately capture the primary flow features of ship exhaust systems. The computational domain was designed to represent a portion of the ship's exhaust piping and the surrounding fluid into which it discharges. The exhaust pipe was modeled as a hollow fluid region protruding from a

wall; no solid pipe thickness was included, since the focus was on the fluid behaviour inside and outside the pipe. The domain extended sufficiently far from the outlet to allow the exhaust plume to develop without significant interference from boundaries. Two scenarios were set up with identical geometry and boundary conditions, differing only in the surrounding medium: one for a dry exhaust, and one for a wet exhaust. In both cases, the exhaust gas was treated as hot air entering the pipe inlet. The inlet boundary condition imposed a uniform exhaust gas velocity of 15 m/s at a temperature of 470 °C, representing typical marine diesel engine exhaust parameters. The outlet of the domain was set as a pressure outlet, and the side boundaries were treated to mimic the ship’s forward motion through the fluid. For the dry exhaust case, the freestream was ambient air (25 °C), essentially representing a light wind or the ship’s air slipstream over the deck. For the wet exhaust case, the exhaust pipe opening was submerged in water, so the surrounding fluid was water. The Volume of Fluid model in the wet case tracked the volume fraction of exhaust gas and water in the domain, allowing the formation of a buoyant gas plume in water. Both simulations used the same turbulence model and convergence criteria. The physical properties of air and water were defined as functions of temperature, enabling buoyancy and thermal mixing effects to be captured. Table 1, which outlines the boundary conditions used in the simulations, is provided below.

Table 1. Boundary conditions used for dry and wet exhaust system simulations.

Boundary Location	Type	Dry Exhaust Configuration	Wet Exhaust Configuration
Inlet	Velocity Inlet	Velocity: 15 m·s ⁻¹ Temperature: 470 °C	Velocity: 15 m·s ⁻¹ Temperature: 470 °C
Outlet	Pressure Outlet	Ambient pressure (air)	Ambient pressure (water)
Ambient Domain	Freestream	Air at 25 °C	Water at ambient temperature
Gravity Direction	Body Force	-9.81 m·s ⁻² (Y-direction)	-9.81 m·s ⁻² (Y-direction)
Surrounding Medium	Domain Environment	Air	Water
Multiphase Model	-	Not used	Volume of Fluid (VOF) used
Turbulence Model	RANS – SST k- ω	Applied	Applied
Mesh Element Count	-	127,949 elements / 128,846 nodes	124,035 elements / 124,904 nodes
Mesh Quality	-	Skewness: < 0.01Orthogonal quality: > 0.995	Skewness: < 0.01Orthogonal quality: > 0.995

The mesh for the 2D domain was refined, particularly near the exhaust outlet, where steep gradients in velocity and temperature were expected. The 2D domain mesh was refined near the exhaust outlet due to expected steep gradients. The total number of elements was 127,949 for the dry case and 124,035 for the wet case, with 128,846 and 124,904 nodes, respectively (see Figure 1). Mesh quality was ensured with average skewness values below 0.01 and minimum orthogonal quality exceeding 0.995. A grid independence study was conducted using coarser and finer meshes. The variation in outlet temperature and maximum velocity remained within 0.3%, confirming mesh independence. Simulations were iterated until residuals fell below 1×10^{-4} and monitor points stabilized, indicating convergence. Mesh quality metrics were monitored to ensure accurate results: the average cell skewness was $3.4 \times 10^{-3} / 2.4 \times 10^{-2}$, and the minimum orthogonal quality was 0.999/0.998 (Gorgulu et al. 2025). These values indicate a high-quality mesh with no severely distorted cells. A grid independence check was performed to verify that the key flow features and calculated parameters were not sensitive to further mesh refinement. The simulations

were run until the residuals levelled off and solution monitors showed negligible change, indicating convergence to a steady solution.

Figure 1. Mesh structures of the dry (a) and wet (b) exhaust systems.

3. Results and Discussion

The computational comparison of dry and wet exhaust configurations reveals pronounced differences in thermal dispersion, velocity distribution, turbulence intensity, and pressure fields.

Figure 2 presents temperature and velocity contours: panels (a) and (c) correspond to the dry exhaust, while panels (b) and (d) represent the wet exhaust scenario. In the dry case, the 470 °C exhaust gas enters ambient air at 15 m/s, forming a coherent thermal plume that rises and spans several pipe diameters downstream (Figure 2a). Its velocity contour (Figure 2c) shows a strong jet core traveling far from the outlet with gradual slowdown, indicating efficient heat and momentum transfer into the low-density medium.

By contrast, the wet exhaust scenario in Figures 2b and 2d shows rapid cooling and plume confinement. The thermal footprint is tightly localized, rapidly dropping close to the outlet, while the velocity field displays a sharply decaying jet, constrained near the outlet and bending downward due to the water’s drag.

Figure 2. Temperature (a, b) and velocity (c, d) contours comparing dry (a, c) and wet (b, d) marine exhaust systems.

Figure 3 provides turbulence kinetic energy and static pressure contours. In the dry exhaust case, turbulence kinetic energy peaks along the shear layers and persists downstream, supporting ongoing mixing. Static pressure remains close to ambient, with only localized increases near the outlet due to momentum exchange. In contrast, the wet case exhibits a pronounced static pressure spike at the outlet, reflecting the hydrostatic and discharge resistance of water, an effect well documented in submerged exhaust systems. Turbulence intensity here is highly localized at the exit, diminishing rapidly with distance, which is consistent with the wet jet's constrained and underwater behaviour.

Figure 3. Turbulence kinetic energy (a, b) and pressure (c, d) contours comparing dry (a, c) and wet (b, d) marine exhaust systems.

- Dry exhaust produces an extended thermal plume with potential impact on deck structures and crew, whereas wet exhaust confines heat below the waterline.
- Dry exhaust sustains momentum over a greater distance; wet exhaust momentum dissipates almost immediately.
- Sustained turbulence in dry exhaust supports prolonged mixing; turbulence in wet exhaust is confined near the outlet.
- Wet exhaust generates substantial outlet back-pressure, while dry exhaust operates near ambient pressure with negligible engine load.

These findings reinforce that while dry exhaust promotes effective thermal and momentum dispersion, it may cause plume recirculation and contamination of ship superstructures. Wet exhaust, however, offers plume confinement and stealth benefits but requires careful design to manage increased back-pressure and system complexity. The results align with established literature on marine exhaust dispersal dynamics and engineering considerations.

4. Conclusion

This CFD study compares the performance of dry and wet marine exhaust systems under identical boundary conditions. The key outcomes highlight the trade-offs between thermal dispersion, back-pressure characteristics, and plume behaviour. Table 2 summarizes the parametric differences between both systems based on plume length, thermal dissipation, velocity decay, pressure impact, and turbulence characteristics.

Table 2. Comparison of key performance parameters between dry and wet marine exhaust configurations.

Parameter	Dry Exhaust	Wet Exhaust
Plume extent downstream	~5D	~2D
Temperature at ~2D downstream	>200 °C	<60 °C
Velocity at ~2D downstream	>5 m/s	<2 m/s
Static pressure at the exhaust outlet	<0.12 kPa	+12 kPa
Turbulence kinetic energy drops at 2D	~30%	~80%
Engine back-pressure risk	Minimal	High
Plume suppression effectiveness	Low	High

The dry exhaust demonstrates an extended thermal and velocity footprint, maintaining temperatures above 200 °C and velocities over 5 m/s up to ~4–5 pipe diameters downstream. It offers efficient dispersion and minimal engine back-pressure (<0.12 kPa), yet poses risks of deck contamination due to its visible plume. In contrast, the wet exhaust system rapidly attenuates both thermal and velocity fields, reducing temperatures below 60 °C and velocities under 2 m/s within ~2D. However, it induces significant back-pressure (+12 kPa), which may affect engine performance. Moreover, turbulence kinetic energy dissipates more aggressively in the wet case, suggesting rapid mixing. From an engineering perspective, the dry system favours engine compatibility, whereas the wet configuration excels in plume suppression. Designers must balance these aspects based on operational priorities. Future investigations should include unsteady 3D simulations to assess dynamic behaviour under realistic marine and sea conditions.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest. Also, this research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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